

A REVIEW OF REFERENCE METHODS FOR AUTOMATED ULTRASONIC EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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Keywords: Automated ultrasonic testing, Non-destructive evaluation,
Quality Assurance, Reference methods, Wind rotor blade

ABSTRACT

Automated ultrasonic testing is an important non-destructive evaluation method for quality optimization and assurance of composite structures. Ultrasonic non-destructive evaluation of composite structures is relevant for a number of reasons. The ultrasonic velocity is related to the elastic properties of a composite and the ultrasonic pulse amplitude is sensitive to laminar defect types. Moreover, automated ultrasonic testing systems provides reproducible images and an operator independent documentation of a composite structure. A problem is, however, that there are limited standards for quantitative validation of ultrasonic images of composite materials, especially throughout the lifetime of the structure. This is due to the fact, that composite structures like wind rotor blades are manufactured from a number of different material combinations and manufacturing technologies. The paper reviews six different reference methods for evaluating ultrasonic images of large composite structures like a wind rotor blade. The reference methods may be applied in the various lifetime stages of the wind rotor blade and establish an automated ultrasonic evaluation of a composite structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a need for optimization of the quality of composite materials used in renewable energy technologies, such as wind rotor blades. The quality of glass- and carbon structures in wind rotor blades is an important topic for both manufactures and turbine operators. However, quality assessments of rotor blades have been a challenge for the entire wind community due to: lack of inspection standards, a demand for more cost effective production and limited accessibility to the blades.

The most commonly applied non-destructive testing techniques for composite structures are visual inspection, tap testing and ultrasonic testing. Ultrasonic testing is one of the most popular techniques due to its high penetration capacity and its sensitivity to defects commonly found in spar caps and web adhesive bondings. Other techniques, mainly optical and thermal techniques, have been developed to address composites, and because these techniques are non-contact, X-ray imaging, shearography, active thermography, terahertz and laser-ultrasonics have become quite popular in the industry [1-2]. The major drawbacks of the mentioned methods for wind rotor blade testing are their limited depth penetration, their limited scanning speed, their potential for damaging the composite structure, and that these methods are still considerably more expensive to automate than conventional ultrasonic methods. A problem is, however, that besides from some aerospace applications there are limited standards for validating ultrasonic images in composite materials [3]. The main reason for the limited standards is, that composite structures in wind rotor blades are manufactured from a number of different material combinations and manufacturing technologies making it difficult, or impossible, for standards to be developed that encompass the material properties at a meaningful level of details. Moreover, as the scale of wind turbines continues to increase wind rotor blades are getting longer and now exceed 80 meter in length [4]. Due to the huge variety of composite materials, it is not possible to address all aspects of reference methods for ultrasonic evaluation of composite structures in this review. The paper first introduces automated ultrasonic testing followed by a description of composite materials applied to large

structures. Six different reference methods are then reviewed for evaluating automated ultrasonic images of composite structures.

2 AUTOMATED ULTRASONIC TESTING

An important method for quality optimization of large composite structures is automated ultrasonic testing (AUT) as it provides reproducible images and an operator independent documentation of the composite structure. Ultrasonic evaluation of a composite structure is particularly relevant as the elastic waves are sensitive to laminar defect types and have a great penetration capacity. To generate an ultrasonic image of the blade, AUT systems use a scanner, e.g. a manipulator or a robot, to move one or more ultrasonic probes in a particular scan pattern. A specific challenge is to scan vertically positioned blades in operational environments. It requires a constant water coupling between the probe and the structure. If the required coupling media is missing, the ultrasonic waves can not be transmitted into the structure. An AUT system designed with the mentioned challenges in mind is the P-scan Stack System [5]. Besides from having a processor module with a high dynamic range (>100 dB) and a high amplitude resolution (22 bit) the AUT system also provides:

- a processor module with a built-in scanner control,
- an automatically controlled water supply with adjustable flow rate, and
- probes with center frequencies in the range from 250 kHz – 10 MHz.

2.1 Initial calibration of the AUT system

Initial calibration of the AUT system is important for sizing defects correctly in all depths of the structure. This is a well-established discipline for metallic structures and based on reference blocks with engineered reflectors [6]. The engineered reflectors are basically divided into flat-bottom holes (FBH) and side-drilled holes (SDH). The FBH's are machined to have a flat reflecting disk-shaped surface giving a signal similar to a smooth crack while the SDH's are drilled into the side of the test block giving a reflecting surface independent of beam angle. However, as the distance between probe and reflector increases a sound field compensation for the decrease in pulse-echo response must be applied. With the reference block, an operator either generates a distance-amplitude-curve by plotting the amplitude of the FBH/SDH at different depths or generates a time-varied-gain (TVG) curve by adding additional gain to each reflected signal. In this way, the reflected signals from relevant depths appear with the same amplitude level. Other initial calibrations of an AUT system may be compensating for the time the sound travels through a coupling "wedge" and setting a reference level in dB for the system.

3 COMPOSITE MATERIALS APPLIED IN WIND ROTOR BLADES

Composite structures in wind rotor blades are manufactured using different technologies from a number of material combinations with dissimilar properties. The structures can be divided into two main categories: laminates and sandwich structures. Fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) for laminate and sandwich skin structures are primarily produced using polymer-based resins as a matrix in combination with reinforcement fibers to increase the stiffness and strength of the matrix. The properties of a single FRP laminate are determined by numerous factors but the most important factors are: the resin and fiber properties, the fiber volume fraction and the fiber orientation. The fibers commonly used in wind rotor blades, in the form of strands, yarns and rovings are glass due to their high specific strength but for longer blades, the more expensive carbon fibers are applied due to their higher stiffness and lower weight. The matrix systems of the structural parts are made of either polyester, epoxy or vinylester resin [7]. The main difference between these thermoset resin types are: *i*) polyesters are low cost, but have a high cure shrinkage and styrene emission; *ii*) vinylesters are more expensive and have better mechanical properties than polyester, but have a high cure shrinkage; *iii*) epoxies have good mechanical and thermal properties but are the most expensive of the three types. Today, glass, carbon and epoxy resins are the most widely used materials in the wind blade manufacturing industry. While most aerospace composite components are manufactured using pre-pregs and autoclave cure, larger structures often use preforms based on dry fabrics manually inserted into a mold. In these structures, liquid resin is infused into the preform and the composite structure is then cured. A variety of manufacturing technologies exist for drawing resin through infusion ports into a sealed dry fiber preform under vacuum. For medium sized

structures, the infusion process is often based on a closed mold, for example Resin Transfer Molding. For even larger structures, like wind rotor blades the infusion is performed using vacuum pressure with a vacuum bag, for example Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding [8]. New technologies for manufacturing large composite structures are continuously pushed by automated processes and advanced material technology.

In summary, the manufacturing methods for composite structures like wind rotor blades are characterized by the manual insertion of glass- and carbon fiber reinforcement into a mold. The process is very labor intensive and results in a relatively low volume output. As the blades get longer this leads to increased variability between blades and an increase in the number of defect types.

3.1 Defect types commonly detected in large structures

The spar cap is the primary load carrying structural part, mainly consisting of unidirectional plies, and it is the aim for nearly all AUT systems to ensure that the blades can complete their designated life span [9]. Figure 1 shows a cross sectional schematic of a wind rotor blade and an illustration of typical defects that may be detected in the spar cap and in bonding regions with AUT.

Figure 1: Cross sectional schematics of wind rotor blade with illustrations of an AUT probe and typical defects in the spar cap and web bonding.

The defects in the spar cap appear typically in different phases of the components lifetime. In the *design* phase of a blade, production subcomponents may be evaluated by AUT to analyze a reason for failure. Examples of the most important defect types in the design phase are: dry areas, porosity (voids), interplay delamination and defects in bonded adhesive joints between the spar cap and shear web. In the *production* phase, detection of the same defect types mentioned above is of relevance but possible fiber waviness, foreign bodies and repair areas may also be verified by AUT as a confirmation of the structural integrity. Consequently, to repair the structure in the proper way, exact location and extent of these defects need to be measured precisely as possible with AUT. For in-service inspection of the blade in *operation*, other defect types are of relevance. The most common defects occurring in the operational phase are: impact damage, fiber waviness, delamination, ingress of moisture, gelcoat debonding and leading edge erosion. A list of defect types commonly appearing in large structures like the spar cap is summarized in Table 1 for their lifetime phases.

Phases	Defect type
<i>Design</i>	Dry areas, porosity (voids), delaminations, defects in bonded joints
<i>Production</i>	Dry areas, foreign bodies, fiber waviness, delaminations, defects in bonded joints, repair areas
<i>Operation</i>	Impact, fiber waviness, delaminations, ingress of moisture, gelcoat debonding or erosion

Table 1: Typical defect types in the spar cap appearing in the design, production and operation phases of wind rotor blades.

4 REFERENCE METHODS

A review of reference methods for evaluating automated ultrasonic images of composite structures is given below. The reference methods are based on either:

- Engineered machined references
- Engineered embedded references
- Computer models as references
- Mechanical testing as references
- Micrographs as references
- Alternative NDE methods as references.

4.1 Engineered machined references

Similar to ultrasonic testing of metallic structures, engineered machined references are often applied to composite structures in order to determine the smallest detectable laminar defect size like delaminations, bonding defects, etc. The engineered machined references may be applied in the form of circular or rectangular FBH's milled into a FRP block of constant thickness. A precise depth and diameter of the holes is required, but this may be difficult to machine in practice. After initial calibration and TVG adjustment, automated ultrasonic scanning of the FRP block is performed in order to determine the smallest detectable defect size in the structure. The TVG ensures that the defect size can be measured independent of the material depth. The method is applied to subcomponent scanning in the design phase and as a reference in the production phase. An advantage of machined holes is that they provide a good reflector as long as they are perpendicular to the surface. Drawbacks of machined drilled references like FBH's are that the method is destructive and that the reference block only can be evaluated from the opposite side of the hole entrance.

An example of a laminate with engineered machined references is seen in Figure 2. An AUT scanner developed for subcomponent inspection was used to scan a 30 mm (1.2 in) thick carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminate with circular and rectangular FBH's. Water flow rate was automatically adjusted and fed to the probe surface to insure sufficient ultrasonic coupling. The dimensions of the laminate were 900x250 mm² and the results were displayed and analyzed as P-scan images with a Top-view, Side-view and End-view. In this case, two circular and four rectangular FBH's can clearly be separated in depth, using sliders, and located in three dimensions. In the example, the size of the FBH is measured to be 50x50 mm². Regions in the laminate with a low amplitude level also revealed evidence of needle voids.

Figure 2: P-scan image of CFRP laminate with engineered machined references.

Figure 3: Principle of embedded fiber waviness (left) and AUT image showing fiber waviness in a GRP laminate (right).

4.2 Engineered embedded references

Engineered embedded references are often applied to simulate more realistic defect types like dry areas, foreign bodies, adhesive bonding defects etc. To control and evaluate specific parameters like the angle of fiber waviness, more complex geometries of the embedded references can also be incorporated. The engineered embedded references, e.g. Teflon implants, resin pockets, wood or wax paper are implanted in the layup and then followed by infusion and curing. This method is applied for subcomponent scanning in the design phase and as a reference in the production phase. An advantage with embedded references is that they look more like real defects compared with machined references and that they can be inspected from both sides of the laminate. A drawback is that the infusion process may change the position of the implants making it difficult to rely on the reference.

An example of a laminate with engineered embedded references is seen in Figure 3. An AUT system was used to scan a 90 mm (3.5 in) thick glass fiber reinforced polymer (GRP) laminate with out-of-plane embedded resin pockets. The result was displayed as a 2000 mm long line-scan image displaying a cross sectional view of the structure. In this case, indications of fiber waviness could clearly be observed and separated in depth due to variations in signal time and amplitude. The line-scan image also shows thickness variations of the laminate and the location of defect types in two directions. Quantitative correlations between the embedded defects and the ultrasonic findings will depend on the specific ultrasonic settings.

4.3 Computer models as references

Computer models of sound propagation in a composite structure may be used to simulate a change in material properties and a variation of the ultrasonic settings [10-11]. In these models simulated defects can be moved and changed into complex forms according to the requirements. Computer simulations are also applied to model defect variations in size, shape, angle and location to provide a probability-of-detection curve [12]. Computer models may be applied in all lifetime phases and one of the advantages of using computer models is that they allow a more flexible AUT investigation and may create complex defect shapes without actually manufacturing reference specimens. In practice, physical reference blocks cannot be avoided, but the required number may be significantly reduced. A disadvantage of computer models is that the established model depends on real input parameters, which may be difficult to obtain.

An example of a computer model based on a CAD model and a semi analytic solution to the wave equation is shown in Figure 4. A CIVA computer model is used to demonstrate a lack of bonding between two carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates while the associated A-scan illustrates an A-scan signal echo from the delaminated bonding area.

Figure 4: Computer model demonstrating a lack of bonding between two CFRP laminates and associated A-scan.

4.4 Mechanical testing as references

Ultrasonic parameters may be compared directly with the elastic properties of the structure. For isotropic materials like steel the ultrasonic longitudinal and transverse velocities (v_L and v_T) are related to the elastic properties simply like:

$$v_L = \sqrt{\frac{E(1-\mu)}{\rho(1+\mu)(1-2\mu)}}, \quad v_T = \sqrt{\frac{E}{2\rho(1+\mu)}} \quad (1,2)$$

Where E is the Young's modulus, μ is the Poisson ratio and ρ is the mass density.

In an anisotropic (orthotropic) structure the velocity, v_{eff} , depends on the combination of elastic constants and the angle of incidence, but may in symmetry planes ($i=1,2,3$) be approximated with:

$$v_{eff} \approx \sqrt{\frac{c_{ii}}{\rho}} \quad (3)$$

Where c_{ii} is an effective elastic constant given by the anisotropy of the laminate.

Mechanical test methods are e.g. regulated after ASTM-standards and described in [13]. A correlation between the ultrasonic velocity and the elastic properties may be established by measuring the ultrasonic velocities in test specimens cut with defined fiber orientations [14]. From the ultrasonic velocity, elastic parameters can be determined in the main directions, although a correlation to mechanical test methods must be done. Compared to steel, composite materials are anisotropic, inhomogeneous and more attenuated. Table 2 compares common physical properties for materials like steel, epoxy resins, glass fiber, carbon fiber, GRP and CFRP. A minimum and maximum is given for the longitudinal velocity in epoxy resins, GRP and CFRP as v_L depends on e.g. temperature, probe frequency, fiber content etc. However, the potential of a correlation between mechanical test and AUT is that the elastic parameters can be determined non-destructively, not only for sub-components but also for large structures. This subject is still under development and further work has to be done for AUT.

Physical property			Steel	Epoxy resin	Glass fiber	GRP	CFRP
Density	ρ	[g/cm ³]	7.8	1.2	2.5	1.4-1.8	1.8-2.0
Velocity L	v_L	[m/s]	5900	*(1200	3150	*(2600	*(2500
Velocity T	v_T	[m/s]	3230	-2500)	1727	-3200)	-3000)
Attenuation	α_L	[dB/mm]	< 0.05	0.5-3.0	0.2-0.4	> 1.5	> 1.5

Table 2: Common physical properties for solid materials. * v_L (min-max).

4.5 Micrographs as reference

Micrographs are digital images taken through a microscope. The images are obtained by cutting samples in selected areas of the structure. It provides a cross-sectional cut of the area of interest and analysis is performed using high-resolution microscopes for determining of e.g. porosity, fiber waviness, dry areas, foreign bodies, repair areas, impact damage and moisture content. The measured parameters can be correlated with ultrasonic parameters like the ultrasonic velocity or amplitude in combination with advanced signal processing. An advantage of micrographs is that detailed information may be obtained, but the disadvantage is that the information, e.g. the porosity content, is selected from a specific sample, which may not be representative for the entire structure. In terms of reliability, it is important that the AUT method is calibrated properly and that the correlation is based on a high number of micrographs to obtain a quantitative evaluation of defects in the composite structure. Figure 5 (left) shows a cross sectional image with porosity. The image is generated with an environmental scanning electron microscope at a high resolution and the porosity content can be estimated according to one of the standards [15]. Figure 5 (right) shows an example of a top-view of a GFR component (1000x300

mm²). The color-coding represents the amplitude variation in the component that must be correlated to the porosity content.

Figure 5: Selected micrograph (left) and AUT image of composite part with porosity (right).

4.6 Alternative NDE methods as references

Alternative NDE methods like visual inspection, tap testing, X-ray imaging, shearography, active thermography, terahertz or laser-ultrasonics may also be applied to establish a reference [16]. X-ray methods are based on intensity changes in the material, while infrared methods determine changes in surface temperature. Alternative NDE methods may provide a correlation to AUT in terms of porosity level, moisture content, dry areas, foreign bodies, repair areas and impact damage. One of the advantages of alternative NDE methods is, that besides the ones mentioned in the introduction, they might establish an interpretation of some of the defects not detected by AUT. One drawback of the alternative methods is that depth determination of defects is difficult for the most common defects types appearing in a spar cap. The variety of alternative NDE methods is out-of-scope for this paper.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The paper reviews six different reference methods for evaluating ultrasonic images of large composite structures like a wind rotor blade. The reference methods are based on either: engineered machined holes, engineered embedded implants, computer models, mechanical test, micrographs and/or alternative NDE methods. The aim of a quantitative ultrasonic material characterization is to create an improved correlation between physical observations and the ultrasonic properties. The reference methods may be applied in the various lifetime stages of the wind rotor blade and establish an automated ultrasonic evaluation of a composite structure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank The Industry's Composite Laboratory and its partnership with The Technical University of Denmark and Aalborg University. The partnership is funded by The Ministry of Higher Education and Science and the aim is to assist companies in developing the knowledge and competences needed in order become established in the composite industry. The author also wants to thank Mr. M. Troedsson and Mr. B. Hornblow for fruitful discussions.

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